

ISic0648

I.Sicily inscription 0648

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2015.10.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8749

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140813

1. ΚΟΥ [— — — — — — — — — —]
2. οὔνομ [ά μοι — — — — — — — —]
3. Πρείμω Κ,Α [— — — — — — — —]
4. πόλλ' ἔπαθο [ν — — — — — — — —]
5. τήνδε γονεῖς κ. [— — — — — — — —]
6. καὶ δεῖνται προφ [— — — — — — — —]
7. εὔχεσθε θεῶ [ὑπὲρ αὐτοῦ — —]
8. ζῆν ἔσορᾶν Υ. [— — — — — — — —]
- 9.

Edition: PHI332937

1. Κου [ίντα(?) □ □ - □ - □ □]
2. οὔνομ [α ἦν μοι - □ □ - □ □ - □]
3. Πρείμω κ [- □ □ - □ - □ □ - □]
4. πόλλ' ἔπαθο [ν □ □ - □]
5. τήνδε γονεῖς κ ἄ [μον(?) - - - □ ταφήν(?)]
6. καὶ δεῖνται προφ [ητῶν □ □ - □]

7. εὐχέσθε θεῶ [— — — — — — —]
8. ζῆν, ἔσορᾶν ὑ,α [κίνθους(?) - □ □ - □ □ - □].
- 9.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492925

EDCS 39101690

PHI 140813

PHI 332937

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0498 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 44.0766

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 44.0738.7

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 106: 79-118. At 94 no.7 fig.14

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0648. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385098>